

ENSURING THE INTELLECTUAL AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN BASED ON PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article talks about the organization of the educational process in preschool education based on pedagogical technologies and their importance, the role of pedagogical technologies in the activities of educators.

Keywords: pedagogical technology, creativity, creativity, ability, skill

ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО И СОЦИАЛЬНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА НА ОСНОВЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится об организации образовательного процесса в дошкольном образовании на основе педагогических технологий и их значении, роли педагогических технологий в деятельности воспитателей.

Ключевые слова: педагогическая технология, творчество, креативность, способность, умение.

INTRODUCTION

The intellectual and social development of preschool children creates the foundation for their educational process at later stages. During this period, the formation of the child's personality, speech, thinking, communication culture, behavior, social relations with others are strongly developed. The role of modern pedagogical technologies in these processes is incomparable. Pedagogical technologies are a scientifically based, systematic and effective way of pedagogical activity aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's personality, and are recognized as an important tool for increasing the intellectual and social potential of children through innovative approaches in preschool education. It is difficult to imagine the rapidly developing field of education without innovative pedagogical technologies. Pedagogical technologies have taken over every aspect of the field of education, including preschool education, and organizing activities based on pedagogical technologies gives effective results. In this regard, we should find answers to the questions "Does every teacher in the organization know what pedagogical technology is?", "Can he use pedagogical technology in his work?", "What is pedagogical technology?". Pedagogical technology (PT) is a field of knowledge that, with the help of which, in the 3rd millennium, fundamental changes will occur in the field of education of our country, the activities of teachers will be renewed, and a thirst for knowledge, love for the Motherland, and feelings of humanity will be systematically formed.

ОСНОВНАЯ ЧАСТЬ

The concept of "technology" entered science in 1872 in connection with technical progress and is formed from the Greek words -technos- art, hunar-valogos-science, doctrine, and means "science of craft". However, this expression cannot fully describe the modern technological process, the technological process always implies the performance of actions (operations) in a certain sequence using the necessary tools and conditions. More precisely, the technological

process is the activity of a worker (worker-machine) to create a product as a result of the step-by-step impact of labor tools on objects of labor (raw materials). The following concepts derived from the word technology are used in production:

Technological process - a set of technological operations that form a single process of processing a manufactured product. Technological operation - a part of the process in the form of an action performed by a worker at his workplace, brought to completion. Technological map - a technical document describing the sequence of technological operations for the production of a particular product. Technological regime - a procedure for determining the implementation of technological operations, determining the timing and conditions of operations performed in the production of a particular product. If we transfer these definitions and concepts to the educational process, we can come to the following conclusion:

Pedagogical technology is a process of influencing students (students) by a teacher (educator) under certain conditions using teaching aids and intensively forming predetermined personal qualities in them as a result of this activity. Pedagogical technology is a systematic category that determines the technologization of the educational process as a whole. The concepts of "teaching technology", "educational technology" are also used in pedagogical publications. Teaching technology - firstly, it means the process-action aspect of pedagogical technology. This is the development and implementation of an educational model that embodies the systematic unity of methods and tools (technological operations) that ensure the guaranteed achievement of the intended results of the educational process in changing conditions, during the allotted time, and the implementation of specific educational and educational processes;

Secondly, it represents the process-descriptive aspect of pedagogical technology. This is a statement of the implementation of the project of pedagogical and educational activities to achieve the goal and achieve the results set in the future (technological map). Educational technology is used to determine the scientific aspect of pedagogical technology. This is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining all processes of teaching and learning, taking into account technical and human resources and their cooperation, which sets the task of optimizing forms of education.

The Russian scientist V.P. Bespalko, who was one of the first in the CIS countries to scientifically substantiate the need to introduce pedagogical technology into the educational process, gives the following definition, saying that "pedagogical technology is a project of a pedagogical system that can be implemented in practice,": "Pedagogical technology is a project of the process of forming the personality of a student, which can guarantee pedagogical success regardless of the teacher's skills." The following important principles can be distinguished from the content of Bespalko's definition:

-PT (Pedagogical technology) is designed to form certain elements of social experience in students;

-The implementation of the designed ready-made technology does not require great skill from the subject teacher;

-The final result is guaranteed.

According to the definition of T.S. Nazarova: "Pedagogical technology is a set of methods and tools used in the educational process to achieve the intended goal of education." According to the definition approved by the authoritative UNESCO organization, "Pedagogical technology is a systematic method for identifying, creating and applying all processes of teaching and learning, taking into account technical means, human potential and their impact, in order to optimize

educational forms.” German scientist Kurt Lewin and Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget, studying the psychological nature of the majority in a group reaching a single decision in the 1940s, emphasized the importance of pedagogical technologies. Pedagogical technology is considered a method of education, in a certain sense, a set of educational processes, tools, forms and methods. "Pedagogical technology is a system for developing and improving educational processes, content, methods and tools of education based on objective laws of education and diagnostic goals." As we can see, there is still no consensus on the definition of the concept of "pedagogical technology". In our opinion, pedagogical technology is a set of educational processes, methods, tools, forms of education, and relationships between teachers and students, requiring a systematic, technological approach to the educational process and reflecting such important features as clarifying educational goals, guaranteeing results, and objective assessment. Also, the tasks of pedagogical technology as a science include determining the content of education at each stage of education, preparing forms and means of education, preparing tests for inclusion in the content of the subject, situational texts, developing a system of tasks aimed at mastering the intended professional qualities and spiritual qualities in a person, and preparing test tasks for objective assessment of the results of education and the level of mastery. In particular, pedagogical technology spread rapidly in almost all developed countries at the end of the 20th century and was recognized and supported by the influential UNESCO organization. Today, it is being successfully used in many countries. Many countries have achieved significant success in developing the education system and increasing student learning using pedagogical technology. The basis of the technologization of education is the idea of complete control over the educational process, its effectiveness and ensuring that students achieve the planned learning outcomes under given conditions and within a specified time. It is also envisaged that with the help of pedagogical technology, fundamental changes will occur in the education system of Uzbekistan in the 3rd millennium, the activities of teachers and students will be renewed, and a thirst for knowledge, individuality, humanity and love for the Motherland will be systematically formed in young people. What does "new pedagogical technology" mean? First of all, pedagogical technology is designed for the educational (educational) process. Each society determines the goal of forming a person, and accordingly a certain pedagogical system is created. This system is continuously influenced by social order and generally determines the content of education.

The goal" in turn leads to the need to update the remaining elements of the pedagogical system. Here we can cite a Chinese proverb as an example. "Tell me, I will forget, show me, I can remember, give me the opportunity to work on myself, then it will be completely mine." Interactive exercises, role-playing games - this is teaching through movement - the most effective way to gain experience, an interesting form of mastering knowledge and skills, and a method that helps children understand how others feel in similar situations. So, the purpose of education has been completely updated, and accordingly, it is natural to update both the content and the pedagogical process. Secondly, with the development of science and technology, the boundaries of human activity are expanding enormously, and new technologies with great educational potential are entering the audience. There are also new technical, informational and audiovisual tools that require new methodologies and are becoming an integral part of the educational process and introducing certain features into it, which have made new pedagogical technologies a real reality. Pedagogical technology is essentially on a par with other technologies, because they, like other technologies, have their own specific field, methods, tools, and work with certain materials. However, pedagogical technology, as a field of knowledge with the human mind, is distinguished

from both biological and even information technologies by the fact that it expresses a complex and not everyone can understand pedagogical process. Now let's consider the methods of applying interactive methods in the organization of preschool education.

CONCLUSION

Preschool age is an important stage that forms the foundation for the formation of a child as a person. During this period, the child seeks to find his place in the activity, thinking, communication and social environment. Pedagogical technologies serve as a guiding, stimulating and reinforcing tool in these processes.

The results of the study show that through interactive and modern approaches (project-based learning, game technologies, ICT, cooperative learning), children's interest in knowledge increases, speech culture develops and social behavior is formed. In particular, a positive effect of role-playing games and theater technologies on the social adaptability of children was observed.

Also, the systematic and targeted use of pedagogical technologies leads to the following results: the child develops independent thinking, questioning and reasoning skills; the ability to understand, analyze and draw conclusions from information increases; the ability to behave in a team, freely express one's opinion, and solve problems is formed; the educator's methodological approaches are enriched and efficiency increases.

However, the following factors are important for the effective implementation of these technologies: continuous professional development of educators; providing MTOs with modern technical means; involving parents in the pedagogical process; strengthening methodological services and systematic introduction of innovative approaches.

In conclusion, pedagogical technologies are becoming not only a source of knowledge for preschool children, but also a powerful factor in personal and social development. Therefore, in modern education, it is necessary to fully integrate pedagogical technologies into practice and serve as a strategic direction for maximum disclosure of the child's potential.

LIST OF REFERENCES USED

1. Bates, T. (2015). *Teaching In A Digital Age: Guidelines For Designing Teaching And Learning*. Tony Bates Associates Ltd.
2. Abdurashidov, A., & Turdaliyeva, N. (2023). Development Of Manual Work In Pre-School Education. *Science And Innovation*, 2(B2), 282-286.
3. Qizi Turdaliyeva, N. A. (2024). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalar Ijodiy Qobiliyatlarni Rivojlantirishning Nazariy Asoslari. *Golden Brain*, 2(7), 48-52.
4. Soliyev Ilhomjon Sobirjonovich, & Boymirzayeva Shakhnoza Olimjon Kizi. (2023). Systemic Organization Of Professional Competence, Creativity And Innovative Activity Of A Future Kindergartener. *Journal Of Pedagogical Inventions And Practices*, 19, 108–112. Retrieved From <https://Zienjournals.Com/Index.Php/Jpip/Article/View/3709>
5. Soliyev, I., & Boymirzayeva, S. (2023). Maktabgacha Ta'lim Tizimida Innovatsion Yondashuvning Uslubiy Asoslari Va Pedagogik Shart-Sharoitlari. *Наука И Инновация*, 1(6), 128-129.
6. Qizi Boymirzayeva, S. O. (2024). Maktabgacha Ta'lim Tashkilotida Bo 'Lajak Tarbiyachining Kreativligini Rivojlantirish. *Golden Brain*, 2(7), 41-47.
7. Orinova, F., & Boymirzayeva, S. (2025). Identification Of Intellectual Abilities Of Students In Preschool Educational Organizations And Their Targeted Development. *International Journal Of Artificial Intelligence*, 1(2), 1604-1609.

8. Boymirzayeva, S., & Mirzaaxmedova, X. (2024). Maktabgacha Ta'lim Tashkiloti Pedagoglarining Hamkorlikdagi Ish Faoliyatini Nazariy Asoslari. *Nordic_Press*, 5(0005).
9. Shahnoza Olimjon Qizi, B. (2025). Pedagogical Basis Of Identification And Development Of Intellectual Abilities Of Children Age 3–7 Through The Use Of Game Technologies In The Preschool Education System. *Advances In Science And Education*, 1(02), 18-21.
10. Boymirzayeva, S. (2025). Tarbiyalanuvchilarning Intellektual Qobiliyatlarini Aniqlash Va Ularni Maqsadli Rivojlantirish Usullariga Qaratilgan O 'Yin Texnologiyalari. Qo 'Qon Universiteti Xabarnomasi, 14, 136-139. Orinova, F., & Turdaliyeva, N. (2025). Developing Creative Thinking Through Handicraft For Preschool Children. *International Journal Of Artificial Intelligence*, 1(2), 1610-1616.
11. Turdaliyeva, N., & Mamadjonova, D. (2024). Maktabgacha Ta'lim Tashkilotlarida Bolalarga Ta'lim-Tarbiya Berishda Ijodiy O'yinlardan Foydalanish. *Nordic_Press*, 5(0005).
12. Nurjahon, T. (2024). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarda Qol Mehnatini Rivojlantirish. *University Research Base*, 456-460.

ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI

1.F.R. Qodirova, N.M. Qayumova, M.N. Agzamova "Maktabgacha pedagogika" Toshkent-2019 –yil,672 b

2. N.T.Tosheva “Maktabgacha ta’lim –tarbiyani tashkil etish” Buxoro-2022-yil,344
3. Sh.O.Boymirzayeva (2024) DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE EDUCATOR IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION. International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences 20-22
- 4.http://ru.wikipedia.jrg/wiki/Metodiy_obucheniya.
- 5.mahoratacademy.uz
- 6.Soliyev Ilhomjon Sobirjonovich, Boymirzayeva Shakhnoza Olimjon kizi. Professional Competence of a Teacher as a Factor of Increasing the Quality of Preschool Education. International Journal of Culture and Modernity. ISSN 2697-2131, Volume 18/July-2022, 95-99 bet.
- 7.Soliyev Ilhomjon Sobirjonovich, Boymirzayeva Shahnoza Olimjon qizi. MAKTABGACHA TA‘LIM TIZIMIDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVNING USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA PEDAGOGIK SHART SHAROITLARI. ILM-FAN VA INNOVATSIYA ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYASI in-academy.uz/index.php/si, 128-129 bet.
- 8.I.S.Soliyev, Sh.O.Boymirzayeva. TARBIYACHILAR KASBIY KOMPITENTLIGINI OSHIRISH, MAKTABGACHA VA BOSHLANG,ICH TA‘LIMNING DOLZARB MASALALARI: MUAMMO, YECHIMLAR VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjumani MATERIALLARI,364-365 bet.
- 9.Soliyev Ilhomjon Sobirjonovich, Boymirzayeva Shakhnoza Olimjon kizi. Systemic Organization of Professional Competence, Creativity and Innovative Activity of A Future Kindergartener. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. ISSN NO: 2770-2367 <https://zienjournals.com> Date of Publication: 10-04-2023. 108-112 bet.